

EFFECT OF FIBER-MATRIX INTERPHASE ON THE TIME DEPENDENT RESPONSE OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the effect of fiber-matrix interphase on the time dependent response of unidirectional and cross-ply composite laminates was studied. Three material systems with the same fiber and matrix, but with different levels of surface treatment (100 % and 200 %) and different sizings (epoxy and thermoplastic) were used. (90)₁₂ and (0,90)₃ laminates were used in this study. Results indicate that the (90)₁₂ laminates of the material systems with different surface treatment levels exhibit similar creep response under room temperature tensile and elevated temperature flexural creep tests. However, the laminates with a thermoplastic (Polyvinylpyrrolidone) sizing exhibited greater creep deformations compared to the epoxy sized materials. Damage analysis results indicate that the time dependent transverse cracking and damage accumulation is different in the cross-ply laminates of the three material systems.

INTRODUCTION

Recent efforts have been directed towards improving the composite performance by tailoring the interfacial bonding condition, in polymeric composites. The interface/interphase in these carbon fiber reinforced composites have been altered by varying the level of surface treatment and/or sizing on the fibers. The results indicate that the strength and long-term performance of composite materials can be significantly improved by altering the fiber-matrix bonding (interface/interphase).

Madhukar and Drzal [1,2] have recently shown that the static mechanical properties of unidirectional laminates depend on the type of interphase present in the composite. They used the untreated AU4 fibers, surface treated AS4 fibers and surface treated and sized (with unreacted epoxy) AS4C fibers in Epon 828 matrix to obtain three systems of composites with different interphases. They attributed the improvement in mechanical properties to the improved bonding in the AS4 and AS4C system. Numerous other studies have demonstrated that the static properties [3,4] can be improved by altering the fiber-matrix bonding.

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Swain [5] has investigated the fatigue performance of Apollo carbon fiber reinforced toughened epoxy (HC 9106-3) laminates. He concluded that both fiber sizing and surface treatment affect the damage mechanisms and fatigue life of notched cross-ply laminates under fully reversed fatigue loading. The authors have recently shown that the damage mechanisms and failure modes in the material system used in the present study are controlled by the interfacial bonding condition under tensile static [6] and fatigue loading [7].

There has however been very little work done to study the effect of fiber-matrix interphase on the time dependent response of polymeric composites. Recently, a systematic study was performed by Chang [8] to investigate the effect of the interphase on creep and creep rupture characteristics of the AS4/J2 (Thermoplastic) system. Results indicate that the degradation rate of the creep rupture strength was not affected by the interphase properties. However, the system with sized fibers (a compliant sizing designated as AS4CGP by the manufacturer) was found to have higher creep rupture strength compared to the unsized AS4/J2 system even though the static strength of these two systems were nearly equal.

In this study, the effect of fiber-matrix interphase on the time dependent performance of unidirectional and (0,90₃)_s cross-ply laminates was investigated. Three material systems with different levels of fiber surface treatment and fiber sizing were used to study the effects of interphase. The presence of different fiber-matrix interphase in these material systems has been reported in earlier investigations by the authors [9]. The room temperature tensile creep response and elevated temperature flexural creep response was studied in three material systems with carefully altered interphases.

MATERIAL SYSTEM

The material used in this study was obtained from McDonnell Aircraft Co., through Dexter Hysol. Three material systems having the same high modulus Apollo carbon fibers (manufactured by Courtoolds Research) and HC 9106-3 toughened epoxy matrix, but with different fiber sizing and surface treatment, were used to study the effects of the interphase. These are designated 810 A, 820 A and 810 O systems. The fibers used in the 810 A and 810 O systems received 100 % industry standard surface treatment, while the fibers used in the 820 A system received 200 % industry standard surface treatment. The 'A' and 'O' represent two different sizing used in the fibers. The "A" sizing is an unreacted Bisphenol-A epoxy and the "O" sizing is Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), a thermoplastic material. The sizing material constitutes less than 1 weight % of the composite in all three material system. Laminates were manufactured by Dexter Hysol as 152 mm x 152 mm panels using an autoclave processing method in (90)₁₂ and (0,90₃)_s layup. 152 mm long and 12.5 mm wide specimen were cut from the unidirectional and cross-ply laminates for tensile creep tests. Dynamic mechanical tests were performed on (90)₁₂ specimens with nominal dimensions of 40mm x 12.5 mm x 1 mm.

TEST PROCEDURE

All room temperature tensile creep tests were performed on a 20 kip servo-hydraulic MTS test machine under load control mode. A 25.4 mm MTS extensometer was used to monitor strain continuously during the creep tests. Tensile creep tests were performed at three load levels on the unidirectional laminate and one load level on the cross-ply laminate. The extent of damage was documented using penetrant enhanced x-ray radiography. The edge replication technique was also used to monitor the progression of transverse matrix cracking in the 810 A and 810 O cross-ply laminates. Dynamic mechanical measurements were made with a DuPont 983 DMA unit. An arm displacement of 0.3 mm was used in all tests. Short term creep tests were conducted between 100 and 185 ° C at 5/10 ° C increments. The cycle consisted of creep loading at a specific temperature for 10 minutes, followed by a relaxation period of 40 minutes

at the next higher temperature. The specimen were not removed from the clamps between tests at different temperatures. The 40 minute relaxation time was used to erase previous loading and thermal history.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flexural Creep Response of (90)₁₂ laminates (Using DMA)

Short term (10 minute) flexural creep tests were performed at various temperatures on (90)₁₂ laminates using a DuPont-983 DMA. Tests were conducted at 10° C temperature intervals between 110° C and 150° C. Since the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the matrix material is around 185° C, tests were conducted at 5° C intervals above 150° C. The variation of creep compliance of the 810 A, 810 O and 820 A laminates were determined using the short term creep tests. The Time Temperature Superposition Principle (TTSP) was used to shift these curves along the horizontal axis to obtain the master curves. The master curves for the 810 A, 820 A and 810 O laminates at a base temperature of 110° C are plotted in figure 1. The figure indicates that the 820 A laminate has the highest initial compliance, followed by the 810 O and 810 A laminate. Also, the 810 A and 820 A laminates exhibit similar increases in compliance with time. In contrast, the 810 O laminates exhibit greater increase in creep compliance compared to the other two material systems.

The horizontal shift factors for the three material systems obtained by TTSP is plotted against the reciprocal of the absolute temperature in figure 2. All three material systems exhibit a bilinear behavior. Since the data indicates a bilinear behavior, the data for each material system are fitted with two straight lines. Similar bilinear behavior has been reported in some earlier studies [8]. This behavior has been attributed to the different molecular motions associated with the transitions at the lower temperatures and at temperatures close to the T_g. It is observed that the change in slope occurs for the 810 A, 820 A and 810 O system at 145, 153, 150° C respectively. These temperatures correspond to the beginning of transition from the glassy state to rubbery state.

Room temperature tensile creep response of (90)₁₂ laminates

The room temperature tensile creep response of 810 A and 820 A laminates at different load levels are displayed in figures 3 and 4. The figures indicate that the creep response of (90)₁₂ laminates of the 810 A and 820 A system are almost identical. The figures indicates that the 810 A and 810 A laminates exhibit limited time dependent response. The maximum increase in compliance after 15,000 seconds is only about 5 %. It is also noticed that in the range of loads tested, the creep response is independent of load level indicating linear viscoelastic behavior. The creep response of the 810 O laminates are shown in figure 5. In sharp contrast to the creep response of the 810 A and 820 A system, the 810 O laminates exhibit greater creep response. The maximum creep compliance change after 15,000 seconds is about 13 %. This is significantly greater than the 5 % change observed in the other two material system. The data also indicate slight stress dependence in the load range used in this study. However, for comparison purpose, a power law best fit curve is drawn through all the data points in figure 5. The solid line in the figure represents the best fit curve. Based on figures 3,4 and 5, it can be concluded that the 810 O system exhibits greater creep response. This is not very surprising considering that the 810 O system contains a thermoplastic sizing material. It is well known that the thermoplastic materials exhibit greater creep response. Even though the sizing forms less than 1 % of the material, the creep response of the material system is dramatically changed. This indicates that the fiber-matrix interphase plays a significant role in the time dependent response of composite materials. In order to verify the presence of damage in the form of matrix cracks and/or fiber-matrix debonding, one laminate from each material system

was x-rayed. The x-ray radiographs did not reveal any damage in the form of matrix cracks or fiber/matrix debonding in either of the three material system. It is thus concluded that the changes in compliance (figures 3-5) represent changes in creep compliance. It is interesting to note both tensile and flexural creep tests indicate that the 810 O system exhibits greater creep response. The 810A and 820 A system exhibit similar creep (tensile and flexural) response and the changes in creep compliance are lower in these materials compared to the 810 O system.

Room Temperature tensile creep response of cross-ply laminates

The normalized creep compliance of the 90° ply in the 810 A cross-ply laminate at 345 MPa load level is shown in figure 6. The creep compliance of the 90° ply was obtained by measuring the compliance of the cross-ply laminate and estimating the change in compliance of the 90° ply using classical lamination theory. It was assumed that the 0° ply behaves as a perfectly elastic material, and the compliance change in the cross-ply laminate is due to creep and damage in the 90° ply. The solid line in the figure indicates the variation in creep compliance of the 90° ply obtained from the (90)₁₂ laminate tests discussed in the previous section. The figure indicates that the constrained 90° ply undergoes greater compliance changes compared to the unconstrained 90° laminates. This is somewhat surprising because the constrained ply is expected to undergo less creep. However, it must be borne in mind that the constrained 90° ply could also undergo damage, while it was established that the unconstrained 90° laminates did not undergo any damage. Also interesting is the increase in compliance observed after about 12,000 seconds. This could be indicative of damage in the form of matrix cracking in the 90° ply of the cross-ply laminate. In order to verify the presence of damage in the cross-ply laminates, x-ray radiography was performed on this laminate. The variation of normalized tensile creep compliance of the 90° ply in the 820 A cross-ply laminate at 345 MPa load level is shown in figure 7. The variation of compliance of the unconstrained 90° laminate is shown in the figure as a solid line. The figure indicates that greater compliance variation occurs in the constrained 90° ply. Again, this could be due to damage in the form of matrix cracks in the 90° ply of the cross-ply laminate. It is interesting to note that the deviation of the compliance curve of the constrained 90° ply from that of the unconstrained 90° ply is the greatest in the 820 A system. The room temperature creep compliance of the unconstrained and constrained 90° ply of the 810 O system at 241 MPa load are plotted in figure 8. The 90° plies in the 810 O cross-ply laminate exhibits greater compliance changes compared to the unconstrained 90° laminate. It is interesting to note that the contribution of damage to the compliance change in the cross-ply laminate is the lowest in the 810 O laminate. This is somewhat surprising, considering that the 810 O laminates exhibited greater damage under static [6] and fatigue [7] loading. It must be borne in mind that the 810 O laminate was subjected to a lower load compared to the other two laminates.

In order to verify if there is any damage in the constrained 90° ply of the cross-ply laminate, specimen from all three material system were x-rayed. Figure 9 shows the x-ray radiographs of these laminates after 15,000 seconds. The figure clearly shows damage in all three laminates in the form of transverse matrix cracks in the 90° plies. This explains the greater compliance changes in the constrained 90° plies of the three material system. It is interesting to note that in the 810 O laminate, there are no transverse cracks extending throughout the width of the laminate. However, there are numerous small transverse cracks in the 90° ply that do not extend through the width of the laminate. The 810 O laminate also reveals a few longitudinal splits in the 0° ply. In comparison, the 810 A laminate has two transverse cracks extending through the width of the laminate, in the gage section. There are no longitudinal splits in the 0° ply of the 810 A laminate. The x-ray radiograph of the 820 A laminate reveals two transverse cracks extending through the width of the laminate. A few longitudinal splits are also seen in the 0° ply of the cross-ply laminate. While comparing the damage in the three laminates displayed in figure 9, it must be borne in mind that the 810 A and 820 A laminates were

subjected to a higher load compared to the 810 O laminate. This could explain the lesser amount of damage seen in the x-ray radiograph of the 810 O laminate.

The progression of transverse matrix cracking in the cross-ply specimen from 810 A and 810 O system was monitored by edge replication technique. Figure 10 shows the progression of transverse crack density in these specimens at 35 ksi load level. The figure indicates that the rate of increase in transverse crack density is almost the same in the two material systems. However, the number of transverse cracks is significantly greater in the 810 O laminate at all times, compared to the 810 A laminate. It must be pointed out that these results are consistent with the damage analysis results reported by the authors under quasi-static loading [6].

SUMMARY

The short term DMA creep results indicate that the 810 O laminates exhibit significantly greater amounts of changes in flexural creep compliance compared to the other two material system. The room temperature tensile creep test on (90)₁₂ laminates indicates a similar response. The room temperature tensile creep tests on cross-ply laminates indicate that the 90° plies in the laminate exhibits creep deformation and damage in the form of transverse matrix cracks and longitudinal splits in the 0° ply. The damage in the 90 and 0 degree ply under creep loading are different in the three material systems with different interphases.

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Figure 1 Creep compliance master curves for $(90)_{12}$ laminates at 110°C .

Figure 2 Variation of horizontal shift factor with temperature for the three material systems.

Figure 3 Variation of room temperature tensile creep compliance of $(90)_{12}$ 810 A laminates.

Figure 4 Variation of room temperature tensile creep compliance of (90)₁₂ 820 A laminates.

Figure 5 Variation of room temperature tensile creep compliance of (90)₁₂ 810 O laminates.

Figure 6 Variation of RT tensile creep compliance of 810 A cross-ply laminates.

Figure 7 Variation of RT tensile creep compliance of 820 A cross-ply laminates.

Figure 8 Variation of RT tensile creep compliance of 810 O cross-ply laminates.

Figure 9 X-ray of cross-ply laminates (15000 sec)
Top : 810 A; Middle : 820 A; Bottom : 810 O

Figure 10 Variation of transverse crack density in cross-ply laminates at RT.